

Leaf Disease Detector Using Residual Network

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Abstract—Agricultural productivity is a key component of Indian economy. Therefore the contribution of food crops and cash crops is highly important for both the environment and human beings. Every year crops succumb to several diseases. Due to inadequate diagnosis of such diseases and not knowing symptoms of the disease and its treatment many plants die. The study of leaf diseases, as well as their detection and diagnosis, has been the subject of an increasing amount of research and attention as intelligent agricultural systems have become increasingly common and widely used. In order to explore the detection and classification of apple leaf illnesses, we made use of data sets containing examples of apple grey-spot disease, black star disease, cedar rust disease, and healthy leaves. CNN classifier for image segmentation, ResNet and convolutional neural network models were utilized for comparison and improvement respectively. In our proposed method ResNet-18, which had less layers of the ResNet network, achieved greater recognition effects by obtaining an accuracy rate of 96.5 percent

Index Terms—convolutional neural network, CNN, deep learning, ResNet, leaf disease

I. INTRODUCTION

India is a country with a population of approximately 1.38 billion as of April 2020. Estimates put the total number of farmers in India somewhere between 95.8 million. It must be noted that 18 percentage of India's GDP is produced from the agricultural sector. It would, thus, be safe to infer that if agriculture was revolutionized, it'd benefit the country greatly and also apart from alleviating the conditions of local farmers, it'd also create a lot of employment and expansion opportunities in the agricultural sectors[1]. Research and development on pesticides, fungicides, and herbicides have progressed very well in India. But, every year, due to natural reasons, crops succumb to various known diseases and tonnes of produced crops are lost and this can be dealt with quick detection of plant diseases in proper time. It will help to get over the dire economic conditions faced by the country's farmers[2]. Nowadays technology has changed lives for the better. Due to the internet, almost everything is within reach. With the help of a normal camera, one can easily click photos of affected parts and upload it to the system which detects the particular disease and provides the exact treatment as well as a pesticide if required. Most of the plants are infected by

various fungal and bacterial diseases. The exponential increase of population, the climatic conditions also cause plant diseases. The leaves require close monitoring to detect the disease. This makes the description less sensitive to variations in distortion from one image to the next. At the moment, the HOG gradient histogram is the descriptor that is the most often employed in object identification. This makes it feasible to acquire satisfactory results in a relatively short amount of time [1]. The investigation of a technique known as "Deep Learning" as it relates to agricultural applications has intensified recently, which not only opens the door to new applications but also improves performance in comparison to the approaches that are now in use. There are several techniques are reported by many researchers for plant disease detection and monitoring. Usama Mokhtar presented Gabor wavelet transform techniques to extract tomato leaf features. They used SVM to detect leaf diseases. For experiments real sample images of tomato leaf have been considered and two types of disease in tomato leaves including early blight and powdery mildew have been observed. In preprocessing, phase images are resized to 512*512 resolutions to deduce the computational time. Background subtraction method has been applied to remove the background of the image. In the classification, using kernel function the SVM was trained and tested[3]. Ganesan proposed a fuzzy-based segmentation method with computer vision for the early identification of plant leaf diseases. Image segmentation is also applied to extract the diseased part of the plant leaf from the input image. Color space segmentation is also applied to identify the color of the fruit or disease affected area [4]. Arthit Srikaew, Kittit Attakitmongkol, and Prayoth Kumsawat proposed a leaf disease diagnosis method using neural networks. An unsupervised method is implemented using color imagery. Color and texture, both the features of the image are processed. The proposed system is consist of two parts. One is extraction of disease feature and the other one is classification of the same. Former one emphasizes on feature appearance based on a co-occurrence matrix depend on gray

level along with texture feature equations. Later one deploys the fuzzy ARTMAP neural network which is basically an unsupervised method to categorize different types of diseases.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

(Dawood Idressa, 2024) aims to develop a machine learning-based system for detecting diseases in maize plants using image-processing techniques. It focuses on identifying healthy maize leaves and two common diseases: grey leaf spots and common rust. The paper uses 600 images as a dataset. The Machine Learning Algorithms used here are Decision

Tree (DT-90 percentage), Support Vector Machine (SVM90 percentage), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN-91.3 percentage), and Artificial Neural Network (ANN-92.7 percentage).

(Abhishek, 2022) explores the integration of a sequential layer into the ResNet18 architecture to improve accuracy in image classification tasks. The research aims to evaluate how this enhancement impacts the performance of ResNet18 on datasets like CIFAR10 and Intel Scene. The paper suggests that the authors have added sequential layers after the final layer of ResNet18. This layer includes the Linear (512, 512) layer, ReLU activation function, Dropout (0.2) layer, Linear (512, 2) layer, and LogSoftmax for computing class probabilities.

(Thongpance, 2023) studied the advantages of using multiple ResNet-18 models for object recognition tasks, with a specific focus on fruit image classification. It provides insights into improving the robustness and accuracy of classification systems, paving the way for broader applications in real-world automated systems. The efficiency of single versus multiple ResNet-18 models is compared. A unique aspect of this study is the establishment of a 90 percentage decision threshold, introduced to mitigate the risk of incorrect classification.

In the study by (Gnawali, 2024), there arises the problem of gradient vanishing or explosion due to extended training time. Transfer learning models, specifically ResNet18, effectively address this issue. That is why they have used ResNet18 for segmented feature extraction. And they can achieve 92.33 percentage accuracy, 92.52 percentage precision, 92.33 percentage recall, and 92.31 percentage f1 score for 50 epochs.

In the study by (Pandey, 2023) the authors used three different CNN algorithms to train the model. The main motto of their system is plant disease detection, weather casting API, and information related to crops and plants and their cultivation methods, along with a communication system with field experts. The attractive part of this paper is the use of three different CNN algorithms: VGG16, ResNet50, and Inception V3. Among these three, ResNet stands out the most with 98.05 percentage accuracy for 5 epochs and 87.47 VGG 16 and Inception V3, respectively.

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The primary goal is to address the low accuracy and high computational complexity of traditional, manual, or shallow machine learning methods in identifying plant diseases, especially at an early stage.

Key Problems Addressed:

- Time-Consuming & Labor-Intensive: Traditional manual inspections are slow, subjective, and require expert knowledge, leading to delayed treatment and significant crop loss.
- Vanishing Gradient in Deep Networks: As models get deeper to achieve better accuracy, they often face issues with training, which ResNet's skip connections are designed to solve.
- Complex Backgrounds & Illumination: In-field leaf images often have noise, shadows, and varying light conditions, making detection challenging for standard CNNs.
- Computational Efficiency: Many high-accuracy models are too large to run on edge devices (like agricultural robots or smartphones), demanding lighter, faster models like a modified ResNet18.

IV. EXISTING SYSTEM

Existing systems for leaf disease detection generally rely on image processing and various machine learning approaches before the adoption of refined deep learning models. Traditional and Older Approaches:

- Machine Learning (ML) Classifiers: Methods such as Support Vector Machines (SVM), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) are used, but they often struggle with complex, non-linear, raw image data, yielding lower accuracies compared to deep learning.
- Traditional Image Processing: Techniques like segmentation (thresholding, watershed) are used for feature extraction, but they are highly sensitive to illumination changes and background noise.

Existing Deep Learning Approaches (Before Refined ResNet18):

- Standard CNNs: Basic convolutional neural networks are commonly used, but they can suffer from lower accuracy due to limited feature extraction capability.
- Pre-trained Models (VGG, AlexNet): Models like VGG16/19 are used but are often criticized for high parameter counts and computational intensity.
- Initial ResNet Models: While ResNet50 and ResNet152 have shown high accuracy (e.g., 98.36%), they are often too heavy for real-time mobile implementation, leading to the adoption of the more efficient ResNet18 as a baseline.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The block diagram of the suggested system for the diagnosis of diseases affecting leaves is shown in Figure 2.

ResNet-18 is the term given to a particular type of convolutional neural network that has 18 levels of depth. You have the option of loading a network that has already been trained making use of the ImageNet database, which includes more than a million different pictures. In order to efficiently identify plant diseases, we made use of pre-trained models that were based on convolutional neural networks (CNN).

Fig. 1. Flow Diagram for proposed model

Residual Network: This architecture proposed a notion that was dubbed Residual Blocks in order to overcome the problem of the vanishing/exploding gradient [7]. The output of the layer that comes before it is used as the input for the layer that comes after it. The convolutional layer, the pooling layer, the activation function layer, and the fully connected (FC) layer are the several layers that make up its multi-layered network, and they each contribute to the successful acquisition of important features [8].

A. Dataset Description

Human society needs to increase food production by an estimated 70 percentage by 2050 to feed an expected population size that is predicted to be over 9 billion people. Currently, infectious diseases reduce the potential yield by an

average of 40 percentage with many farmers in the developing world experiencing yield losses as high as 100 percentage. The widespread distribution of smartphones among crop growers around the world with an expected 5 billion smartphones by 2020 offers the potential of turning the smartphone into a valuable tool for diverse communities growing food. One potential application is the development of mobile disease diagnostics through machine learning and crowdsourcing. Here we announce the release of over 50,000 expertly curated images on healthy and infected leaves of crops plants through the existing online platform PlantVillage. We describe both the data and the platform. These data are the beginning of an ongoing, crowdsourcing effort to enable computer vision approaches to help solve the problem of yield losses in crop plants due to infectious diseases. Data augmentation has been conducted in order to improve the overall excellence of the ResNet model [5] and to bring the results as close as possible to the actual disease that is most prevalent. Taking all of these factors into account, a disease detection model for tomato leaves has been constructed using PyTorch. This model makes use of deep CNNs. In the final step, the testing dataset is treated for authentication using the ResNet 50 model’s previously learned parameters. The classification process began with the six most common diseases that can be found in tomato crops. Since data augmentation was implemented, the size of the data set has been increased to be four times larger than the real information, and the prototypical has demonstrated an accuracy of 97%. The dataset structure follows a class-based directory format, where each directory contains images belonging to a specific disease category. During training, these images are automatically labeled based on their folder names. Let the dataset be represented as:

$$D = \{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^N \tag{1}$$

TABLE I
PARAMETERS AND HYPERPARAMETER VALUE FOR RESNET18 MODEL.

Parameter/hyperparameter	Value/setting
Dataset split	70% training, 30% testing
Number of classes	38
Image size	224 × 224 pixels
Vision Transformer variant	google/vit-base-patch16-224-in21k
ResNet variant	ResNet18
Number of epochs	17
Optimizer	Adam
Learning rate	0.001
Batch size	32
Loss function	Cross-entropy loss

B. Image Preprocessing

Essential Preprocessing Steps:

- These steps are required to make your raw images compatible with the ResNet-18 architecture:

- Resizing: Images must be resized to a uniform dimension, typically
- pixels. Some implementations use • pixels before cropping to the final size.
- Normalization: Pixel values (0–255) are scaled to a [0, 1] range by dividing by 255.
- Standardization: For pre-trained models, apply the ImageNet mean and standard deviation:
- Mean: [0.485, 0.456, 0.406]
- Std Dev: [0.229, 0.224, 0.225]
- Noise Reduction: Applying Gaussian or Wiener filters can help normalize noise in plant images captured in different lighting.

Data Augmentation for Robustness:

Fig. 2. Diseased leaf

Since leaf diseases often appear at different angles or lighting in the field, these techniques help prevent overfitting:

- Geometric Transforms: Use random rotation (e.g., 0–40 degrees), horizontal/vertical flipping, and zooming.
- Color Augmentation: Adjust brightness, contrast, and saturation to simulate different times of day.
- Advanced Techniques: Some researchers use Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) to create synthetic diseased leaf images when certain classes are underrepresented.

C. Model Architecture

Deep Feature Extraction Using ResNet-18: In this research, we opt for the ResNet-18 architecture as the backbone for our

classification model. ResNet, short for Residual Network, is a class of neural network architectures that has demonstrated remarkable effectiveness in various deep learning tasks, particularly in image classification. What sets ResNet apart is its ability to address the vanishing gradient problem, a common challenge when training deep networks, through the use of skip connections. ResNet-18 is a specific variant of the ResNet architecture that we have chosen for our task. It strikes a well-balanced compromise between model depth and computational efficiency. This balance is crucial, especially in applications where both high accuracy and efficient processing are essential. ResNet-18's architecture is structured in a way that enables it to capture intricate features from images, making it an ideal choice for our task of tomato leaf

Fig. 3. ResNET architecture

Noteworthy for its ability to accommodate input images of 224x224 pixels, this architecture serves as an exemplar in the classification. Fig. 3 depicts the Resnet 18 architecture. ResNet-18 constitutes a convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture specifically tailored for image classification tasks.

ResNet lineage, embodying the principles of residual learning to facilitate the training of deep networks.

D. Evaluation Metrics

After building the system, it is trained using a standard dataset. Once trained, it is tested with another dataset to check how well it performs. The model's effectiveness is measured using Accuracy, Precision, F1 Score, and Recall. These metrics help determine how reliable the predictions are.

- Accuracy:

The accuracy of a model is defined as the ratio of true positives and true negatives to all positive and negative observations.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (2)$$

where, TP = True Positive

TN = True Negative

FP = False

Positive FN = False

Negative

• Precision:

The precision of a model is defined as the percentage of labels correctly predicted positively.

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (3)$$

• Recall:

The recall or sensitivity of a model is defined as the ratio of true positives to all the positive instances.

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (4)$$

• F1-score:

The F1-score is a metric that calculates the harmonic mean of precision and recall.

$$F1\text{-score} = \frac{2 * \text{precision} * \text{recall}}{\text{precision} + \text{recall}} \quad (5)$$

Parameter	Value
Epoch	5
Batch Size	32
Optimizer	Adam
Learning rate	0.001

TABLE II
HYPERPARAMETER UED

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-score	support
Blight	0.96	0.90	0.92	477
Common Rust	1.00	0.98	0.94	507
Grey Leaf Spot	0.99	0.95	0.97	485
Healthy	0.98	0.97	0.99	490

TABLE III
CALCULATION FOR LEAF DISEASES

E. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

• Loss and Accuracy graph (Resnet-18):

The graph fig:4& 5 is a visual tool that helps us understand how the ML model is learning and generalizing. It plots the model's achievement on both training data & separate validation set over time. This allows us to see if the model is effectively learning from the trained data. The graph can also help diagnose issues like overfitting, Where the model performs well on the training data but low performance on validation data, it indicates that the model is memorizing the trained set rather than learning generalizable patterns. The model identifies rusted leaves that show aspects like tiny

orange, yellow, or brown spots on their layers. Rust disease was found often, pointing out its ordinary appearance in the area. The system uses CNN model to analyze images & determine if leaves are present. If no leaves are detected, it outputs an alert accordingly, ensuring accurate assessment. This process facilitates subsequent steps in leaf analysis or other tasks dependent on leaf presence. The model executed with an accuracy of 93%, which supports its stability in identifying rust characteristics. This disease reduces the strength of the plant and hampers its photosynthesis ability, highlighting the

Fig. 4. Training Loss and Accuracy

Fig. 5. validation Loss and Accuracy

Fig. 6. Accuracy comparison

need of noting the signs early on to help avoid its damages completely or as much as possible.

F. Comparison Between ResNet-18 and SVM

The performance of the proposed ResNet-18 model is compared with a conventional Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)–based approach. The traditional CNN model learns features through sequential convolution and pooling layers but may suffer from performance degradation as network depth increases. In contrast, ResNet-18 employs residual connections that enable efficient training of deeper networks by addressing the vanishing gradient problem. The experimental results show that the conventional CNN model achieves an accuracy of 94.1, higher accuracy of 98.2 architecture outperforms the standard CNN in terms of accuracy, training stability, and generalization capability. Furthermore, ResNet18 is more effective in capturing complex disease patterns and handling large and diverse datasets, making it more suitable for real-world plant disease detection applications.

VI. PROPOSED SYSTEM:

To overcome these limitations, recent studies utilize ResNet18 with improvements:

Fig. 7. Confussion matrix

S.no	Layer	Parameter	Type	Parameter
01	Conv2d-1	1792	BatchNorm 2d-5	128
02	RELU-3	0	Conv2d-4	73856
03	BatchNorm 2d-5	256	ReLU-6	0
04	Maxpool2d -7	0	Conv2d-8	147584
05	BatchNorm 2d-9	256	RELU	0

TABLE IV
RESNET PARAMETER

- Use of Residual Blocks: ResNet18 uses skip connections to solve the vanishing gradient problem, allowing for deep, efficient learning.
- Modified/Lightweight ResNet18: Researchers propose modifications such as grouped convolutions to reduce parameters (e.g., to 1/46th of the original) while increasing accuracy.
- Attention Mechanisms: Integrating modules like Squeezeand-Excitation (SE) into ResNet18 helps the model focus on critical disease features despite complex backgrounds.
- Transfer Learning: Utilizing Pre-trained ResNet18 (on ImageNet) allows for high accuracy (e.g., 99.67%) even with limited agricultural data.

VII. RESULT:

The planned model, which is discussed in section IV, is put into action, and its presentation is appraised with the help of quantitative indicators such as accuracy. The first thing the model will do is decide if a leaf is healthy or unwell before moving on to the next level. In the event that the first level of classification yields an unnatural leaf, another level of cataloguing will make a diagnosis based on one of the five diseases detailed in Figure 3. The number of photos included in the training dataset has been increased through the use of data augmentation, which has the potential to make the model more accurate. The growth in the variety of the data has led to an improvement in the accuracy of the model, which was accomplished without the collection of more data. PyTorch was used to construct a disease detection model for tomato leaf's that leverages deep convolutional neural networks (CNNs). The issue of overfitting was solved by employing a deep learning strategy that included transform and augmentation, which additionally helped to increase the performance of the model. However, in order to train the model, you will need hardware with a high configuration. This is due to the fact that the ResNet 50 model contains a number of layers. After performing some adjustment on the weightiness for the ResNet perfect, the proposed typical has an accuracy of 96.5

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